

Baptists in Jamaica, 1780-1832

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The first Baptist missionary arrived in Jamaica in 1783 when George Liele, a former slave who had lived in South Carolina and Georgia arrived with over 1,270 white and 4,000 Black Loyalists. Liele had been ordained in the Baptist Church and began preaching to free Blacks around Kingston. He began with a small group in a private home, and then with four others from America traveled around Kingston recruiting followers. In 1789 he purchased a lot of land on which to build a church, many of whose members were enslaved people. Liele was aware of the potential for slaveholders to complain, and so he was careful to be clear that there were no tithes expected from members, and that members must have written permission from their owners allowing them to attend. He also made it clear that he supported himself and his family through other endeavours rather than from the church. With the aid of early recruits to the ministry Nicholas Swigle, George Gibbs, and Moses Baker, the Baptists soon had a strong following which spread throughout the island. Through the movement of enslaved people being sold and one of his assistants being invited by a planter to preach to his bondspeople on a plantation at another part of the island, the Baptist Church quickly grew and included some whites. After appealing to the Baptist Missionary Society in London, missionary John Rowe arrived in 1814, and was soon followed by others. Their primary focus was educating and evangelizing bondspeople. In December 1831, a charismatic deacon named Sam Sharpe became known as the prime leader of a rebellion of enslaved people known as the "Baptist War," the "Christmas Rebellion," and "Sam Sharpe's Rebellion." Although enslaved, Sharpe's job allowed him to travel around a large area of the island, preaching as he went. The impetus for the uprising was fairly complex and came at a time of amelioration of conditions for bondspeople, but primarily revolved around the mistaken impression that orders for emancipation from England were being kept under wraps by the authorities in Jamaica. Originally conceived as a work stoppage by the leaders, most of whom were Baptist deacons, a bloody rebellion ensued which lasted over ten days and which resulted in massive property damage and the deaths of over 300 Blacks and fourteen whites. It was the third in a series of major rebellions in the British Caribbean between 1816 and 1832, all of which are credited with speeding the British government toward emancipation. Following the Baptist War, Baptists suffered property damage, harrassment, and imprisonment. However, the original Baptist faith and a group known as Native Baptists, which had sprung out of a desire for separation from English Baptists who were perceived as prejudicial toward Afro-Jamaicans becoming ministers, continued in popularity into the present day.

Date Range: 1780 CE - 1832 CE

Region: Caribbean

Region tags: Caribbean, Jamaica

Jamaica

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Craton, Michael. "Testing the Chains: Resistance to Slavery in the British West Indies" (Ithaca and London: Cornell University Press, 1982)
- Source 2: Edmonds, Ennis B. and Gonzales, Michelle A. "Caribbean Religious History: An Introduction" (New York: New York University Press: 2010)
- Source 3: Bebbington, D. W. "Baptists Through the Centuries: A History of a Global People" (Waco, Texas: Baylor University Press, 2018)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1558/blth2008v6i3.366>
- Source 1 Description: Lawes, Marvia. "A Historical Evaluation of Jamaican Baptists: A Spirituality of Resistance"
- Source 2 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01440399508575156>
- Source 2 Description: Little, Thomas J. "George Liele and the rise of independent black Baptist churches in the lower South and Jamaica"
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/650070>
- Source 3 Description: Reckford, Mary. "The Jamaica Slave Rebellion of 1831"

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: play.google.com/books/reader?id=seICAAAQAAJ&pg=GBS.PA20&hl=en
- Source 1 Description: Clark, Rev. John, Dendy, Walter, and Phillippo, James Mursell. "The Voice of Jubilee: A Narrative of the Baptist Mission, Jamaica, from Its Commencement; with Biographical Notices of Its Fathers and Founders"
- Source 2 URL: play.google.com/books/reader?id=seICAAAQAAJ&pg=GBS.PA20&hl=en
- Source 2 Description: Baptist Missionary Society. "Narrative of certain events connected with the late disturbances in Jamaica and the charges preferred against the Baptist Missionaries in that island"
- Source 3 URL: <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/mb?a=listis&c=750772690>
- Source 3 Description: Books and serials on Jamaica under the British Empire, from the abolition of the slave importation trade (1807) through the beginning of World War (1914)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: For more information see Little, Thomas J. "George Liele and the rise of independent black churches" cited in Sources

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: All were welcome. The primary cultural group within this religious group were bondspeople and free Blacks.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: As this religious group espoused spiritual equality, they were viewed with suspicion and some fear by white slaveholders.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: In late 1831-early 1832 one of three major uprisings of enslaved people occurred in Jamaica. Referred to as the "Baptist War" and "Sam Sharpe's Rebellion" among other titles, what began as a refusal to work was interpreted by slaveholders as a Haitian-style revolution. Baptists had long been viewed by slaveholders as a danger to the status quo in the same way as other Protestant dissenter denominations had been considered throughout the British Caribbean. For more information see Craton, Michael 'The Baptist War: The Jamaican Rebellion of 1831-1832' in "Testing the Chains: Resistance to Slavery in the British West Indies": 291-322, cited in Sources.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: This answer is a qualified "no" in that it refers only to Jamaican Baptists in this time period. Baptists had experienced conflicts through much of their history, but this group did not have violent conflicts with groups outside of Jamaica.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Public declaration and baptism.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Historically, more Baptists tended to be middle- and lower-class.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Public baptism.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– I don't know

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Because of fears of inciting rebellion among the enslaved, the Jamaican government passed laws in 1808-1809 prohibiting Black ministers from preaching and teaching literacy to the enslaved, as well as prohibiting meetings from areas where it was felt rebellion could be planned. See Lawes, Marvia "A Historical Evaluation" cited in Sources.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

Notes: Rebuked and excluded from group.

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Yes

Notes: Qualified "yes" in that the punishment/cursing would mean inability to enter heaven.

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Qualified "yes" in that this could mean that the apostate was consigned to hell for punishment.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As many of the adherents of the group were enslaved, records are not available which would indicate numbers in each area of the island.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As many of the adherents of the group were enslaved, records are not available which would indicate numbers in each area of the island.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Notes: The Baptist denomination spread quickly throughout Jamaica by way of enslaved adherents being sold from place to place, meeting in urban areas such as Kingston, and through the work of leaders taking up preaching in various areas.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: The leader (pastor) had deacons who were appointed by the congregation and served as advisors.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Groups of Baptists were spread throughout Jamaica, not all of which had a pastor or missionary at its head. Some were primarily run by deacons who were trained under the leaders. Baptists were considered independent churches in that, although connected by faith, one was not subject to another.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the

sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 2

Notes: A missionary or pastor of a particular church or churches and deacons. See answers to "Multiple religious communities each with its own leader" above.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– I don't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Bible.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Although the scriptures were written in the Christian Bible, a large number of adherents during the years in question in Jamaica were enslaved and tended to be illiterate, so there was a dependence on oral scripture.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: Dependent on interpretation of the word of Christian god.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, if Jesus Christ considered supernatural.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Dependent on interpretation of Christian scripture.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: New Testament - teachings of Jesus Christ as son of God to disciples.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: New Testament books of various disciples.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Not alterable, but interpreted into more modern language.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals were free to consider their interpretation.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: While missionaries were the official interpreters, members were free to discuss.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: At this time and place the leader and any deacons or assistants, particularly since many of the congregation would be illiterate bondspeople.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The books of the Bible.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Some purpose-built churches, which survive into present day although largely added to and renovated.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although there were some Baptist churches built for the purpose in Jamaica during this

time period, many gathered where there was space available. In some communities, church buildings would be smaller in size and number than in a more populous area.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: This is most likely unknown precisely as most of the still-existing larger early Baptist churches have been added on to or otherwise renovated. The first Baptist church, built in Kingston between 1789 and 1793, measured 57' x 37' and sat on a three acre lot. See Little, Thomas "The Rise of Independent Black Baptist Churches" cited in Sources.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: This is most likely unknown precisely as most of the still-existing larger early Baptist churches have been added on to or otherwise renovated.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: This is most likely unknown precisely as most of the still-existing larger early Baptist churches have been added on to or otherwise renovated.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: This is most likely unknown precisely as most of the still-existing larger early Baptist churches have been added on to or otherwise renovated.ea.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: This is most likely unknown precisely as most of the still-existing larger early Baptist churches have been added on to or otherwise renovated.ea.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Not significantly for the time period.

Is iconography present:

– I don't know

Notes: Any iconography which was present in the greater number of places of worship would be very simple symbology such as a cross. This was generally a poor, enslaved group of parishioners, with many of their leaders coming from the same background.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Dedicated places of worship such as churches.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Notes: More specifically oriented to demographic features, such as accessibility, number of roads nearby, etc. See Little, Thomas "George Liele and the rise of independent Black churches" cited in Sources.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: As in Christian Bible. The Christian doctrine of life after death was particularly noted to impress upon enslaved adherents that they would be free of their physical suffering in the afterlife.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: See above answer.

Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The concept of parishioners' souls belonging to God and not a human master was of particular importance for enslaved adherents.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Although "heaven" and "hell" were not specifically described in terms of location, they were generally thought of as "above" and "below."

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven for the good; hell for the bad.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven, where God dwelt, was vaguely "above" for those who lived good lives .

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: Hell was vaguely defined as "below" where those who did not live good lives were tormented for eternity.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: See above in terms of "above" and "below."

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: Not for that Christian group at that time.

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: usual in Christian burial at that time.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Assumed laid on back, legs and body extended, but this might not have been followed for all enslaved, particularly at times of a large number of corpses, for example, following rebellion.

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: See above answer regarding flexed corpses.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

- ↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :
 - No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

- No

Are grave goods present:

- No

Notes: Unlikely, as many were enslaved and lived in poverty and did not have many possessions.

Are formal burials present:

- Yes

- ↳ As cenotaphs:
 - No

- ↳ In cemetery:
 - Yes

Notes: There are a number of Baptist cemeteries in Jamaica dating from the time period. Many Baptist bondspeople would be buried in unmarked graves.

- ↳ Family tomb-crypt:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
 - No

- ↳ Other formal burial type:
 - Field doesn't know

Notes: While it is not possible to know the location of all members' burial sites, it is likely some were not buried in a formal cemetery.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

- Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Some characteristics. Humans seen as being made in the Christian god's image.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The idea of the Christian god being "above" can be understood in the context of a sky deity.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: omnipotence and omnipresence

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of

human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: All-knowing.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

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↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
Notes: Can cause anything to occur.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: Events can be seen as a result of god's pleasure.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: Events can be seen as the result of god's displeasure.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No
Notes: This answer should be qualified, as scripture says that no other gods should come before God. However, God's son, Jesus Christ, was also worshipped.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: omnipresence

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No
Notes: Generally, no, although the scriptures describe communication with specific individuals, and some missionaries would describe their vocation as a "calling" from God.

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because each Baptist group was somewhat independent, it would depend on how "God speaking" was interpreted. The basic belief was that God speaks through the scriptures.

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As with other aspects of Baptist groups in Jamaica, each group was somewhat independent and could differ. It is quite possible that a form of trance possession was practiced, as it has been in some other Baptist churches.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

Notes: See notes under Communication With the Living. The scriptures describe various types.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Would depend on individual belief.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– I don't know

Notes: If the common Christian belief in angels was present, in all likelihood there was a belief that non-human supernatural beings were present.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Generally thought of as angels. Some may have considered Jesus Christ as a supernatural being.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: For a perspective of Jamaican Baptists' beliefs of the era, see Clark, Dendy, Phillippo "The Voice of Jubilee" cited in Sources.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The prosocial norm adherence as conforming to the group's beliefs and behaviours.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: In places of worship such as churches or other gatherings.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: If including Christian symbology such as the cross as a sacred object.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Following Christian precepts, Ten Commandments, and other scripture.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Not killing another is one the Christian Ten Commandments.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Not killing another is one the Christian Ten Commandments.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Not killing another is one the Christian Ten Commandments.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Considered wrong to engage in sexual relations outside of marriage. In reality, the practice was common among the enslaved for a number of reasons, such as forceable separation from spouse, marriage not recognized by slaveholders, and the very common practice of enforced sex by owners on their bondpeople.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Not approved of in Christianity or culturally.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Common Christian and cultural aversion to practices outside of that which prescribed in Bible.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Lying against one of Christian Ten Commandments.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Particularly in reference to upholding Christian doctrine such as the Ten Commandments.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Most Christian denominations found laziness to be a bad character trait. As many of the adherents were enslaved, it was to their detriment to be seen as lazy because of the extreme punishments meted out by slaveholders.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: The blanket term for African-based healing rituals was "obeah" which was commonly seen as sorcery among Christians and as being generally anti-Christian. However, it was well-documented culturally, so was likely practiced by some Baptists in Jamaica. For further information, see Paton, Diana "The Cultural Politics of Obeah: Religion, Colonialism and Modernity in the Caribbean World: (Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press, 2015)

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: If it is assumed that supernatural beings such as angels watched over adherents, one of the Christian Ten Commandments is to love one's neighbour, as well as missionaries promoting harmony between spouses

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If "shirking risk" was to be interpreted as an enslaved member disobeying their master or otherwise rebelling, this is hard to answer definitively. The "Baptist War" of 1831-32 was lead by Baptist Sam Sharpe and others; however, this is not directly related to specific considerations of supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Culturally, Christians are expected to respect elders.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: This could be seen as going against the Christian commandment not to "bear false witness" against another. However, within slave studies, "gossip" is often used as simply a way to transfer news and information among a population in which a large number were illiterate.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: One of the Christian Ten Commandments is not to steal.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Of particular importance to Baptists is the ritual of baptism by immersion in water. With this ritual adherents are publicly stating their faith in Jesus Christ by the same ritual as they believe Christ did with his disciples.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: See above notes regarding ritual observance and baptism. Regular services carried out by ministers or deacons were also an important aspect.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Of particular importance to missionaries in the time and place covered here for bondspeople, it may be assumed that any supernatural beings would care about this. See Little, Thomas "George Liele and the rise of the independent Black churches" cited in Sources.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: This is a qualified "yes" given the importance of calls for fair treatment and emancipation among enslaved Baptists. The accused leaders of the 1831-32 rebellion, known as the "Baptist War" and "Sam Sharpe's Rebellion" were leaders and deacons. The inference here is that God/Christ/angels cared about the welfare of the enslaved.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This has not been a topic raised. It must be considered that, especially for the enslaved in Jamaica, personal hygiene would not be important given their oppressive situation, extremes of hard labour, and lack of resources.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: If sent to hell, Satan would be the instrument of punishment.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: Although god decrees who goes to heaven or hell in the afterlife, Satan metes out punishment. In some Protestant interpretations, Satan had minions in hell, but unknown what this group in particular believed.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Considering that God believed to be all-powerful and can cause events to occur.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Notes: Considering that God believed to be all-powerful and can cause events to occur.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Expected to live by Christian tenets and attend worship, if possible.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Following Christian tenets inhibits selfishness, particularly following Christ's example.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Notes: No, in the sense that punishment given for not following scriptures, therefore

ritual-devotional adherence.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: The emphasis tended toward extreme punishment.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The idea of not being with God in heaven in the afterlife and being consigned to Hell to suffer punishment was fairly uniform in Protestant Christianity at this time.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is not a belief within Christianity.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is not a belief within Christianity.

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– I don't know

Notes: While such punishments are sometimes a belief in Protest Christianity, it does not appear to be raised among missionaries in this particular place and time. Considering that most of the parishioners were enslaved, they were already suffering greatly. There was no indication that their oppressed state was a punishment for anything.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: The only way to get to heaven in the afterlife is through following the Bible.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Strong sense of community among group members.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

Notes: Part of Christian belief to treat others as you would wish to be treated and to follow Christ's example.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The core belief was that the only way to reach heaven and be with God was to follow the Ten Commandments and Christ's teachings.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: The idea of sensory pleasure is not emphasized; rather, the focus is on spiritual joy. Although, for people who have been enslaved, it could be considered that the absence of oppression was a sensory pleasure.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: The idea of sensory pleasure is not emphasized; rather, the focus is on spiritual joy. Although, for people who have been enslaved, it could be considered that the absence of oppression was a sensory pleasure.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: Christianity does not consider reincarnation.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: Christianity does not consider reincarnation.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Being with God in heaven was the greatest reward.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: Not the focus because there were so many enslaved and oppressed Baptists at this time.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: Refers to Jesus Christ in Jerusalem. Died, and arose from death.

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Refers to Jesus Christ in Jerusalem. Died, and arose from death.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The second coming of Christ the messiah is a question which remains unanswered today in Christianity. There is no documentation which specifies a date among the LMS documents.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Notes: See above answer regarding second coming in this lifetime.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: The idea of a second coming of Christ the messiah at an unknown time is prevalent in Christianity.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: The idea of a second coming of Christ the messiah at an unknown time is prevalent in Christianity.

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: Part of Christian belief. Generally, the second coming would signify the end of the world as known when all good Christians would be gathered to god.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: Although Christ's primary importance was not seen as a political figure, he became one through his actions offending Roman rulers.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

Notes: Christ the messiah added to Jewish traditions to form the basis of Christianity, although Judaism remained.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Christ the messiah was seen as the son of God who was born in human form. He was to act as a teacher of God's will.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unknown time in Christian theology.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: Unknown time in future according to Christian theology.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unknown in Christianity whether in near or distant future.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: Unknown in Christian theology whether in near or distant future.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Only known to be at some future time.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: Follow Christian doctrine as given in the Bible.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: Good to be rewarded in heaven; others punished in hell.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– I don't know

Notes: Varies according to interpretation. Unknown specifically what was believed by all groups of Jamaican Baptists at this time.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This was not a focus for Jamaican Baptists at this time.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Social norms as to certain behaviours among adherents. Following the Ten Commandments and advice of scriptures were social norms in that formed a basis of how to live and treat others.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: This question is difficult to give a definitive answer because of the status of most of the adherents to the group. Because they were primarily enslaved people, they were generally unable to have autonomy to follow convention or not. The emphasis would be more based on moral distinctions if they were able to follow Christian precepts. For example, an enslaved woman would often not want to commit adultery with a white man, but the convention in that place and time was that Black enslaved women were to be taken at a master's will.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: Part of Christian Ten Commandments.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

Notes: Qualified "no." While Christianity normally espouses peace, the leaders of the 1831-32 rebellion known as the "Baptist War" were Baptists leaders and deacons.

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: Christians in general were expected to show courage in holding fast to their beliefs, although being enslaved, many of the adherents of this group could not act against their master's wishes. However, during the 1831-32 rebellion known as the "Baptist War" members of this group showed great courage in defying slaveholders.

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: A basic Christian tenet.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: A basic Christian tenet.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: A basic Christian tenet.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: A basic Christian tenet.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Notes: A basic Christian tenet.

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Although this is a part of Christianity, as most of the adherents of this group were enslaved they did not have control over many aspects of their lives.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: This was of particular importance for enslaved members to avoid punishment by slaveholders.

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: As part of basic Christian doctrine to honour one's parents, this was an important virtue. However, because most of the adherents were enslaved, they were not always able to follow this precept if it would run contrary to a master's commands.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: Particularly among members of the local Baptist community. This was evident in the aftermath of the 1831-32 rebellion known as the "Baptist War" when it was realized how coordinated the insurgents were without those around them being aware, including, in some cases, their church leader. See Craton, Michael "Testing the Chains": 291-322, cited in Sources

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: This is a qualified "yes" in that the answer refers to the independence of separate Baptist groups and the fight for freedom present in the 1831-32 rebellion known as the "Baptist War."

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: It was difficult for the adherents to display anything other than moderation/frugality if they were enslaved or otherwise lived in poverty.

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: A tendency in most Christian doctrine, this was particularly important among the

primarily enslaved adherents. Missionaries, leaders, and adherents frequently ran into trouble with those in power in Jamaica, being jailed and/or severely punished.

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

Notes: Because of the enslaved status of many members and the difficulties which missionaries and leaders ran into with those in power, at least the outward show of these traits was not wise.

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

Notes: Spiritual strength was emphasized rather than physical.

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: This is not part of basic Protestant Christian tenets, particularly among groups such as these Baptists. Many adherents were enslaved, therefore they possessed none of these.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: Among the basic Protestant Christian tenets, particularly in this instance where most adherents were enslaved and missionaries and leaders were generally not of the upper classes.

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: While such virtues were generally encouraged by Christian missionaries in any case, since most of the adherents at this place and time were enslaved it was particularly important so as to avoid punishment and/or being denied access to worship.

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: This is a very qualified "yes." While it was expected that an adherent would find joy in their faith and hope of salvation, many were enslaved and extremely oppressed or otherwise lived in poverty making it unrealistic to expect these traits in daily life.

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: Optimism and hope in obtaining reward in the afterlife was an important part of the Baptist faith. Otherwise, enslaved people had very little reason for either.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Generally a part of Christianity. While the enslaved adherents had very little to be thankful for, they would be encouraged to be thankful for finding God, and for what little they had.

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: Reverence or awe toward God is a basic Christian precept.

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Most of Christian doctrine is based on faith. For the many enslaved Baptists in Jamaica, they had little else but faith and belief in reward in the afterlife.

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: As Christians, Jamaican Baptists would be encouraged to follow scripture in these traits.

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: Deacons of the church were chosen from among the (male) parishioners who showed the greatest understanding of scripture and were known for their good judgment. Parishioners could be admonished and eventually turned out of the church for repeatedly acting against Christian teachings and/or causing trouble.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: Not important in Christianity.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

Notes: While culturally, most Christian groups value cleanliness, this was not something that could be much controlled among the many enslaved adherents who lived in extreme poverty and who were forced to work most of their waking hours.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The basic important virtues have been covered here.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: While this is expected in the Baptist faith, in reality the situation among the many enslaved members could be difficult in that family units could be broken up due to being sold or transferred, even though through some of this time period the practice was not technically legal.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: While this is expected in the Baptist faith, in reality the situation among the many enslaved members could be difficult in that family units could be broken up due to being sold or transferred, even though through some of this time period the practice was not technically legal. This restriction could be problematic in that a woman might be committed to one partner, but enforced sex by slaveowners was common, in which case the woman was not held at fault if it was not her choice.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: As with most Christian groups, sex outside of marriage was frowned upon.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: As with most Christian groups, sex outside of marriage was frowned upon. Missionaries, leaders, and members recognized that females were always at risk of enforced sex by slaveowners.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: This would be considered murder and against Christian law.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: This would be considered murder and against Christian law.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: This is against Christian law.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Although donations would be welcomed, it was not a requirement, particularly since many lived in extreme poverty and those who were enslaved had little or no personal property. George Liele made it clear that tithes or other payments were not required because of the extreme poverty of many

parishioners. See Little, Thomas "George Liele and the Rise of Independent Black Churches" cited in Sources.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Regular attendance at meetings and worship would be required, except if kept away by slaveowners or managers, or because of illness.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Physical risk taking was in no way required; however, merely being at a Baptist meeting could risk a beating or other punishment by overseers, slaveholders, or other officials.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, members were often marginalized by others.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Although private prayer was encouraged, enslaved members were usually working most of their waking hours and would have no time for formal prayer or worship.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Expected to participate in regular Sunday worship.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There were many groups throughout Jamaica in this time period and they varied in size.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: Because there were many separate groups throughout Jamaica at this time, it is difficult to know how often each met. At the very least, there would be a ritual/worship every Sunday (seven days).

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– I don't know

Notes: Because of the large number of Baptist groups present at this time in Jamaica, it is difficult to say that every group was checked for orthodoxy. It was unlikely. However, there was a great deal of movement throughout the island by some and differences were known.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As with orthodoxy, because of the large number of Baptist groups present at this time in Jamaica, it is difficult to say that every group was checked for orthopraxy. It was unlikely. However, there was a great deal of movement throughout the island by some and differences were known.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: The kinship terminology of "brother" and "sister" was used, as well as, in some cases, "uncle" and "aunt".

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There were many Baptist groups in during this time period and it would be difficult to say that the practice was universal.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– I don't know

Notes: Because of the large number of Baptist groups in Jamaica at this time, many of which did not leave documented evidence of such terminology usage, this is difficult to ascertain.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– I don't know

Notes: Because of the large number of Baptist groups in Jamaica at this time, many of which did not leave documented evidence of such terminology usage, this is difficult to ascertain.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Jamaica was part of the British Empire.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: If famine affected the group's adherents, the entire island of Jamaica would be affected.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Many of the group's adherents were enslaved workers.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Many of the group's adherents were enslaved workers.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Many of the group's adherents were enslaved workers. Although during this time period some ameliorative laws were put in place to better conditions, in reality such people received little care.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Many of the group's adherents were enslaved workers. Although during this time period some ameliorative laws were put in place to better conditions, in reality such people received little care.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Missionaries, leaders, and literate members would teach any of the group's adherents where they were able, depending on slaveholders' allowance of this.

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Particularly after 1823, when ameliorative laws came into effect, educating the enslaved was considered an important aspect of "socialization" in advance of their potential of becoming free in the future. However, some slaveholders were opposed to education in the belief that literacy would lead to rebellion.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: A missionary or other leader was at the top, with several deacons who acted as liaisons between

the leader and the group working under the leader. Some churches could lack an ordained minister due to either inavailability or being away from the area temporarily. In this case one of the deacons would assume leadership until replaced by someone ordained.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Government officials.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: Not as an institution. Enslaved members would labour in some form of water management as part of their jobs on plantations or in towns.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management was the job of any enslaved labourers assigned to it, whether or not they belonged to this group. They were under orders from either plantation managers or government officials.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: As with water management, enslaved workers who were members of this group or not and were assigned to the job worked on transportation infrastructure.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As with water management, enslaved workers who were members of this group or not and were assigned to the job worked on transportation infrastructure.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Although donations were appreciated, there were no tithes as many of the group were enslaved people who lived in extreme poverty. See Little, Thomas "George Liele and the rise of independent Black churches" cited in Sources.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This would only pertain to non-enslaved members, which did not make up the majority of adherents.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group were subject to laws which could be enforced by the local militia or regular military, particularly during events like the 1831-32 rebellion known as the "Baptist War." At various times Baptist missionaries and leaders were imprisoned for preaching to the enslaved. During the rebellion the militia was particularly noted for their cruelty toward enslaved insurgents. See Craton, Michael "The Baptist War" cited in Sources.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Subject to the laws of Jamaica, adherents could be tried in official courts. During the 1831-32 rebellion when martial law was enforced, judges presided over trials of insurgents in a military capacity.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment could include admonishment and being turned out from the church.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Ostracism, while not official, could be seen more as a consequence for missionaries and leaders, particularly for offences such as preaching to the enslaved. These leaders could be jailed for this offence.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: This was of particular note during the 1831-32 rebellion known as the "Baptist War" when some places of worship and houses were destroyed.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The only code, per se, was implied by Christian precepts, but these were not a legal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The laws of England and Jamaica.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Non-enclaved adherents could serve in the militia.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They were subject to the regular military and the colony's militia. Theoretically, they were probably protected by them, but they were, in fact, used against them during the 1831-32 rebellion.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: They used English.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Those who were literate used English.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: hose who were literate used English.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The group used the same calendar based on the Julian calendar as other Western Christian groups.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same Julian-based calendar was used throughout the Western Christian world.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Qualified "yes" in that some slaveholders provided some food. See answers to questions below.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Depending on the specific Baptist group, some slaveholders would supply some or all food for enslaved members. It was not uncommon for bondpeople to have allotted provision grounds in which they could grow some crops and/or raise small numbers of livestock for their own consumption or trade.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Not specifically an institution, but slaveholders would provide some or all of the food for their bondpeople.

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Many slaveholders in Jamaica provided food for their bondpeople, although not necessarily enough or of sufficient variety. The crops and livestock for this function were primarily raised in "pens" which were smaller farms than the large plantations and were dedicated for food supply rather than large-scale trade in commodities such as sugar. For further information on food production and other aspects of enslavement in the British Caribbean, see Higman, B. W. "Slave Populations of the British Caribbean: 1807-1834" (Barbados: The University of the West Indies Press, 1995).